

PRACTICE HEADED PAPER

PRACTICE ADDRESS

PRACTICE PARTNERS

<Potential Participant's address>

<Date>

Dear <Potential Participant name>,

Invitation to join a research study: The SAFER Wearables Study

[DELETE AS APPROPRIATE] {We are writing OR We wrote to you recently} to let you know about a research study that we are involved with. We are working with the SAFER research team from the University of Cambridge.

Firstly, the SAFER research team would like to thank you for your contribution to the SAFER research programme. The programme is looking at how to identify atrial fibrillation (AF), an irregular heartbeat which can increase one's risk of stroke if not treated. The recordings you took using a handheld device (shown below on the left) have been very valuable. They will help determine whether screening for atrial fibrillation (AF, an irregular heartbeat) reduces the incidence of strokes.

The first study

The second study

Secondly, the research team would like to invite you to take part in a second study: the SAFER Wearables Study. New wearable devices can monitor your heart, such as the wristband on the right. The study aims to find out how acceptable they are to users, and whether they can accurately identify atrial fibrillation. You will not need to attend an appointment, and can take part from home. You can still take part if you have atrial fibrillation. Further detail is provided in the enclosed information sheet.

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You do not have to participate. Your decision will not affect any future health care you receive.

Please read through the enclosed information sheet, and if you might be interested in taking part then please telephone the research team on **01223 331 063** to discuss it further. If you are not interested then we would appreciate it if you could return the anonymous Reply Slip to them indicating why you do not wish to take part (as detailed below). {(Note: If they do not hear from you we may send you a reminder letter.)}

Thank you for considering taking part in this second study.

Yours sincerely,

<signature>

<Name of GP>

What to do next:

✓ I AM INTERESTED in taking part

If you are interested in taking part then please read the enclosed information sheet, and telephone the study team on **01223 331 063** to discuss it further.

X I DO NOT want to take part

If you do not wish to take part, we would appreciate it if you would complete the Reply Slip enclosed and return it to the study team in the Freepost envelope provided (no stamp required). We would appreciate it if you would let the researchers know the reasons why you do not wish to participate in the SAFER Wearables study.